

The Effectiveness of Promotion through Brochure Advertising on Merchandise Sales: A Case Study of Multiple Retail Stores of Pakistan

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Abstract

Advertisement plays a significant role in generating awareness and persuasiveness among consumers. Retailers are using brochures to create an awareness regarding promotion of products. Various studies using different price promotional policies reveal that it has significant positive impact on the sales. Customers are very specific on those products that are listed as promotional products. The purpose of this study is to find the presence of promotional brochure at retail stores of Pakistan and how information provided on promotional brochures has an impact on sales. For this purpose, the retail scanner information was used to assess the impact of promotional brochures on sales. The brochures were also collected to identify whether the product is on promotion or not. Regression analysis was applied, and the result showed that different stores have significant effect on sales of the merchandises. Price promotion ensures a positive influence on the sales at the retail level. The result of the study showed that the different products during the promotion from multiple retail stores have positive significant effect on the merchandise sales, brochure advertising have positive significant effect on the retail sales on the multiple retail stores of Pakistan. The findings also showed that the brochure advertising effectively explains the variation in the sales.

Keywords: Brochure advertising, Retail Stores, Promotion, sales

1. Introduction

Marketing is the art and science of analyzing, producing, and providing value to satisfy the demand of a target market at a profit. It focuses on providing value to customers to maximize the firm's profit. Marketing management is a technique of rational about the business, rather than just selling goods and collecting money (Lee & Kotler, 2011). The application of marketing management in business firms has led to an awareness of the importance of finding satisfactory solutions to complex marketing problems that have resulted in the change in the economy. Advertising is a form of marketing statement used to convince an audience to take or endure actions, usually related to a profit-making offering or political or sociopolitical support. There are various models to examine advertising problems, such as the comprehensive Newlove Arrow model, diffusion model, and advertising oscillators model. Advertising choices are often made in small situations and must respond to changes in market situations across time. A different promotion model, including the rivalry between two or more firms, looks at rivals as players in a model and uses distinctive comparisons to model market share growth (Tsai & McGill, 2011).

Advertising is often proposed to remain a supporting factor in a promotion, as retailers increasingly target specific consumers or buyer segments based on their loyalty agenda information and retailer ability to extract such figures. A trendy appearance of value promotion is to turn customers into customers by promoting their purchase yield by remarkable value (Seggie et al., 2007). Brochures serve as an essential intermediate to build customer awareness of the compact and promotions in the face of a broad tendency of diminishing manuscript distribution. Promotion assessment needs to be included or corresponding through the respite of promotion, mainly product brand name conclusions, to successfully provide and complete the promotion mix approach (Libai et al., 2010). Advertising and marketing are essential aspects of business operations that direct the flow of products and services from manufacturers to promoters. These activities begin with identifying a specific need of sales and end with the satisfaction of that need (Arora et al., 2008). The marketing mix consists of factors such as product, price merchandising, placement for products, and three additional factors for services: method, humans, and physical evidence (Joseph & Sivakumaran, 2009).

Promotion is one of the factors of the advertising mix, and retailers make advertising choices to influence customers to buy products and increase prices. These decisions are made simultaneously with other choices like locating target institutions, determining objectives, budgeting for advertising, launching new products, and distribution. Marketers are concerned with the powerful use of promotion blend to grow sales and market proportion (Ailawadi et al., 2009). Price promotion is the interest that seeks to influence customers to buy products and increase prices. It involves incentive-presenting and interest-growing activities, such as short-term advertising, private advertising, exposure, and direct advertising. The purpose of price promotion is to stimulate, inspire, and influence the acquisition and desired behavioral responses of the firm's sales. Product promotions are a significant component of viable situations input on the market with retailers via numerous promotion techniques to create a center of attention for customers. Nowadays, price promotion expenditures report for more than partially all of manufacturer advertising resources. The profound reduction promotion approach, which promotes items at bottomless discounts to catch the attention of consumers who will obtain additional benefits, is widely used by retailers. Promotion is a vital component of a company's marketing mix, and it is often proposed to be a sustainable component in a promotion mix. Promotion assessment must be included and correlated with the rest of the promotion mix, mainly product brand decisions, to successfully support and complete the promotion mix approach (Cody et al., 2002).

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A brochure is an effective way to provide information to existing and potential customers. It serves three functions: informative, promoting, and empathy. An informative brochure informs consumers about your company, such as your employer association, new inventions, or a new name change. A promotional brochure is a significant tool for selling products or services, and a well-designed brochure design ensures a consistent message. A well-designed brochure is crucial for a company's corporate image and can be used to launch an advertising and marketing campaign. Promotions can provide consumers with utilitarian and hedonic benefits, with utilitarian benefits offering high-quality products at discounted prices and reducing searching and decision-making costs. Hedonic benefits, on the other hand, relate to emotions of happiness and excitement (Tahir & Abu Bakar, 2007). Advertising plays a crucial role in marketing consumers, influencing their judgment and preferences. It helps businesses build a corporate image, familiarize customers with new products, and alert them to the impact of promotions on retail sales (Kachadourian et al., 2005). Price promotions can increase customer understanding, product reliability, and variety fairness. The landscape for price promotions has changed, with increased discount sizes and the potential for negative effects on consumer behavior. However, marketers can mitigate the negative effects of price promotions by implementing a broad strategy that balances the positive and negative effects on job promotional sales (Xia et al., 2004).

1.1. Objectives for the Study

- To identify the factors relating to the brochure advertising at retail stores of Pakistan.
- To identify the effect of promotion through brochure advertising on retail sales.
- To suggest implications for retailers regarding the effectiveness of brochure advertising.

2. Review of Literature

This research examines the impact of price promotion and advertising on retail stores' performance and sales. It focuses on the role of category management in retail control initiatives, focusing on how a shift to category management impacts equilibrium costs, income, and profitability in a competitive retail setting. The study examines how retailers invest in business promotions while producers may not provide them (Hosken & Reiffen, 2007). The research also explores how consumer efforts, such as nonmonetary sacrifice, influence their value and protection equality perception in the context of price promotions. The study reveals that the sales flat of effort is a compact value inspiration of their equality insights when they refuse the promoted value. The study also examines the concept of rate promotion fairness, which refers to customers' perceived fairness of the promotion tactics used to decide the promoted price (Sigué, 2008). The research also examines the role of new technology in price and promotion decisions, focusing on the accountability of new permitting technology and recommending significant opportunities for further exploration. The study also examines the impact of price promotions on customers' critiques of the store's regular costs, focusing on the efficiency of different types of promotions (Kim, 2011).

The research also discusses the need for price promotion tactics to be improved in developing markets, particularly in developing markets with limited income. The study proposes a theoretical model that explores the effect of the middle-class sector on price promotion tactics, revealing opposing outcomes. The research also explores the impact of promotions on buyer passage and the usefulness of trade promotions for managers and scholars. The study aims to provide a new systematic method for estimating the impact of promotions on buyer passage and sales (Grewal et al., 2011). In this study, researchers examined the impact of token promotional pricing on sales and found that token promotions can be more effective and make better sales when offered at a small token price rather than free. The results suggest that customers are more likely to respond positively to coupons than open improvements, which may be a complementary effect from regular comparisons. The study also explored the influence of promotional discounts on store presentation metrics, using a store intensity dataset and 24 samples. The results showed that attribute promotions construct lay-up traffic, particularly when the category is popular and high in frequency. Promotions of identified items are considered more valuable than promotions of unbranded items. The study also examined the relationship between loyalty and retail pricing techniques, finding that feelings and untried assumptions are the primary input into this choice. Practitioners lack strong evidence to guide their actions, and their questions are often in stark contrast with intellectual knowledge about the usefulness of price promotions. The study aimed to provide a meta-view of the whole price promotion research system and identify areas for future research. Feng et al. (2017) examined the impact of proportional charge promotions on customer judgment of price reductions, finding that customers take longer to subtract the financial bargain and are less unique than when such promotions existed vertically. The study also examined the impact of loyalty on merchandising strategies for two commonly bought customer package deal goods categories. Technology is transforming the promotion function in various industries, such as cinema, where digital technologies have provided new distribution channels and opportunities for cross-channel results. This paper examines cross-channel outcomes between films offered in virtual buy and digital charge markets, estimating personal and go charge elasticity, and determining whether price reductions impact sales for the same product in a potentially tough channel. In conclusion, token promotional pricing has significant implications for sales and marketing strategies, with various studies exploring the relationship between loyalty, promotion, and cross-channel effects.

Borah et al. (2020) explore the impact of price claims on sales and perceived earnings, with a focus on using just below frames, which include up to 39% off. This study provides managerial implications for using price promotions as a promotional tool. Carlson & Kukar-Kinney (2018) examine the impact of different price advertising consequences on

customer perceptions of bargain credibility, discounts, and change in purchase intention for online daily deal promotions. The study provides government references for store and daily deal managers to use direct online price promotions and daily settlement promotions.

Breugelmans & Campo (2016) emphasize the importance of multi-channel grocery stores' help strategy across channels. Promotions in one channel can have significant negative effects on shopping in the other channel, especially if the promotions range across channels. The study examines the pass-channel outcomes of charge promotions on class purchase selections, taking into account both contemporary and cross-duration outcomes. Lin & González-Rivera (2016) examine the impact of price promotions on producer, store, and customer performance in a supply chain. They also examine the role of retailer involvement in presenting charge promotions to customers. Phillips et al. (2015) investigate the impact of promotions competing for interest and engagement on smooth flow in supermarkets. The study uses binary logistic regression to study consumer behavior and suggests that retailers should focus on observing aisles and complementary products. Ailawadi et al. (2014) study a model of customer solutions to promotions where consumers' delivery of promotional rewards is uncertain. The model incorporates customers' risk aversion and their non-public judgment of the opportunity to receive praise. The study estimates the usefulness of conditional rebates, which are more cost-effective than sure rebates due to sales' subjective opportunity of the event occurring being higher than market intelligence. The study by Xu et al. (2018) explores the decision of a monopoly seller to promote a specific product, focusing on the impact of merchandising on the demand for its other products. The authors propose a model where sales move from low to high-quality products when the latter's rate is reduced. This model suggests that fee advertising gives consumers a starting point to learn about the high-quality product, leading to a few trials. Kang & Kim (2017) highlight the importance of merchandising in the US casino industry, highlighting the significant impact of promotions on gaming revenue. They also highlight the importance of inn room promotions and promotions of other businesses, including F&B, in boosting gaming revenue. Scriven et al. (2017) examine the buying of brands at both daily and promotional rates over time to understand customer deal-proneness. They find that most sales buy brands on promotion at least some of the time, and the tendency to shop for on promotion is usually low. However, the amount of on-deal shopping is usually very little higher than anticipated given the amount of advertising. Haans & Gijbrecchts (2011) discuss the challenges of anticipating promotion increases and profitably managing promotion sports across stores. They study the impact of saving size on the category sales effectiveness of four promotional indicators, finding that sales will increase lower in large stores. Valette-Florence et al. (2011) assesses the relative effect of long-term brand control, logo personality, and short-term marketing mix, sales promotions, on logo fairness formation. They find a fine impact of logo persona and a negative effect of price advertising intensity on brand fairness at the aggregate level. DelVecchio & Smith (2005) argue that price promotions can set preference but can be offset by undermining choice for the brand when it is not promoted. The study provides insights for marketing approaches and understanding the impact of promotions on brand preference.

3. Methodology

This study was begun by examining the literature regarding the effectiveness of promotion through brochure advertising on merchandise sales. The methodology used to resolve the applied complications and growth of information. (Hackley & Hackley, 2014) described those three diverse methods of research; explanatory, descriptive, and exploratory. Descriptive method used to recognize or organize the origins and appearances of definite problem, occurrence or condition that are established by the conceptual model or theory. Exploratory method is distinct as to categorize the source and affect association of the clear position or experience. Explanatory method is assumed to search the realities. The goal of this study is to feature for designs, hypothesis or thoughts that may be established and settled for additional investigation. A significant phase in leading any investigative study is embracing an efficient and suitable technique. Subsequently expressing the study or particular purposes, improve a suitable methodology to conduct a comprehensive study. Method delivers the scholar a trail to comprehensive the procedure of collection, investigation and explanation of facts in stripe with definite research purposes. Methodology may be considered keen on two parts; Qualitative investigation and quantitative investigation. The data collected from multiple retail stores of Pakistan, the number of observations are 1061 and these observations are directly related to sales of different products that are on the promotion on multiple retail stores of Pakistan. Most important is that the sales are related to those products which are on promotion through brochure advertising (Xu et al., 2018).

3.1. Conceptual Framework

We explored that the perception about promotion through brochure advertising has an impact on sales which are related to different products that are being advertised through brochures by multiple retail stores as promotional products or selected items. In results, the sales of these different products increase while the promotion is active through brochure advertising. Following conceptual model indicates that the promotion through brochure advertising has impact directly on the sales while products mediate this relationship.

- i. Sales
- ii. Promotion through Brochure advertising

Figure 1: Conceptual Model

The study requires the wider atmosphere to cover the whole province or country but due to some restrictions as a student researcher like resources availability and as a result of various other elements. This study is conducted in Pakistan of Punjab province of Pakistan. This is one of the main cities from Punjab province taken purposively for the current study on account of the largest and highly populated city of Pakistan. Selection of different products from multiple retail stores was most important in the study because these promotional products of the retail stores approach the consumers as these products are plays an important role to increase the retail sales.

3.2. Data Technique and Procedure

A direct observation technique is used for the collection of data and for the persistence of data collection from multiple retail stores. Data were collected from 1st December 2022 to 20th April 2023. After the data collection procedure the direct observations were tested accurately for the purpose to mark all reactions had been noted properly. The data were attached to (STATA) data analysis software. Multiple regression method was used to quantify the effectiveness of merchandising via promotion through brochure advertising on sales with associated variables. Simple Regression turned into used which gives a better interpretation of variables by estimating coefficients. The coefficient determines how strongly independent variables affect the established variable. The connection among structured and unbiased variable is given:

Where,

Sales = f (bonus, surf excel, lipton, deer tea, dalda oil, store 1, store 2, store 3, weight, promotion)

$$S = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Bonus} + \beta_2 \text{Surf excel} + \beta_3 \text{Lipton} + \beta_4 \text{Deer tea} + \beta_5 \text{Dalda oil} + \beta_6 \text{Store 1} + \beta_7 \text{Store 2} + \beta_8 \text{Weight} + \beta_9 \text{Promotion} + u_i$$

Where, S shows sales and the sales is the dependent variable in this study. For this research secondary data were used. Secondary information series method includes facts which have been combined from multiple retail stores of Pakistan, Punjab Pakistan. Secondary data on brochure advertising and retail sales were collected by using the direct observation method by visiting the retail stores of Pakistan on regular basis. The brochure is one of the effective ways to provide information to the existing and potential customers. There are three functions of brochures, and everyone has an extraordinary manner to be designed.

A brochure serves various functions, including informative, promotional, and emotional functions. It informs consumers about your company, its association, new inventions, or changes to its name. It is a significant marketing tool that allows you to sell products or services, and it is essential to have a well-designed brochure to maintain a consistent brand.

Promotions, which communicate the product, symbol, or service to the public, are crucial for a company's success. There are various types of promotions, including advertising, press releases, sales promotions, and public relations. Price promotion serves three vital roles from a marketer's perspective: inform, persuade, and remind prospective and current customers about a company and its products. The importance of these roles varies depending on the situation.

The maximum benefit of a product or emblem can be a failure if nobody is aware of it. Manufacturers should inform middlemen, consumers, and business customers about the product, while wholesalers should inform outlets and stores. As the number of potential customers grows and the geographic dimensions of a marketplace expand, the issues and prices of informing the market increase.

In summary, a brochure plays a vital role in promoting a company's products, attracting customers, and establishing a strong brand image. It is essential for businesses to consider the importance of price promotion and other promotional strategies to effectively communicate their products and services to their target audience.

4. Empirical Results

The current study was an attempt to know about the effectiveness of promotion through brochure advertising on merchandise sales. Evaluating advertising consequences can be more of a skill than a science. After the data collection, the analysis and interpretation of statistics are the most critical element in every study. Without the analysis of records, it isn't always viable to simplify the goal of the research. For the examination of this study regression and frequency

distribution were used to identify of functions and attributes of statistical samples. The facts were analyzed by means of the use of Stata (version 12). The objective of this study is to determine the promotional regularity of brochure advertising at retail stores of Pakistan and also to identify the effect of promotion through brochure advertising on sales. In this paragraph, we examine the impact of price promotion on appearance of retail sales where the possibility of favorable price promotion is satisfactory. Firstly, by detecting the brochure advertising's effects on the retail sales, it can exist, when the assumption is satisfied, the price promotion still beneficial for the retail sales through brochure advertising. Secondly, in promotion, the assumptions are satisfied, the results are sophisticated. In regression analysis R^2 measures the energy and route of a linear relationship between the two variables; dependent variable (Sales) and the independent variable (Promotion through brochure advertising).

Table 1: Effectiveness of Promotion through brochure advertising on Merchandise Sales

Description	Values
R^2	0.5183
Adjusted R^2	0.5141
Root MSE	1414.3

The R^2 value in this research is 0.5183 that explained all the measured independent variables in this exemplary create 52% variation in the dependent variable. The F-test is designed to check the overall significance. This suggests that the model is overall significant.

4.1. Descriptive Statistics

Mean is the regular numbers and from time to time it is called the arithmetic mean. Enhance all the records in usual and then split the quantity by the whole computation of records. Standard deviation is an indicator to use as a degree of the dispersal or discrepancy in distribution, equivalent to the square source of the mean of the squares of the deviations from the arithmetic mean.

The Table 4.2.2 indicates that the mean of Bonus is 0.015 and its standard deviation is 0.122, if the bonus is on promotion than we consider it as 1 and if the bonus is not on promotion than we consider it 0 and here the value is less than 1 so it is considered as 0. Surf excel mean is 0.012 and its standard is 0.110, Surf excel is considered as second product in research as showed in table 4.2.4 its value is 1 which means that the Surf excel is on promotion if surf excel is not on promotion than its considered as 0, Lipton mean is 0.005 and its standard deviation is 0.069, if the Lipton is on promotion than we consider it as 1 and if the Lipton is not on promotion than we consider it 0 and here the value is less than 1 so it is considered as 0. Deer Tea mean is 0.012 and its standard deviation is 0.110, Deer tea is considered as fourth product in research as showed in table 4.2.4 its value is 1 which means that the Deer tea is on promotion if surf excel is not on promotion than its considered as 0, Dalda oil mean is 0.015 and its standard deviation is 0.122, Dalda Oil is considered as fifth product in research as showed in table 4.2.4 its value is 1 which means that the Dalda Oil is on promotion if Dalda Oil is not on promotion than its considered as 0, Sunsilk mean is 0.015 and its standard deviation is 0.122, if the sunsilk is on promotion than we consider it as 1 and if the sunsilk is not on promotion than we consider it 0 and here the value is less than 1 so it is considered as 0. Store 1 mean is 0.038 and its standard deviation is 0.191, if the store 1 is on promotion than we consider it as 1 and if the store 1 is not on promotion than we consider it 0 and here the value is less than 1 so it is considered as 0, Store 2 mean is 0.020 and its standard deviation is 0.139 Store 2 is considered in research as showed in table 4.2.4 its value is 1 which means that the Store 2 is on promotion if Store 2 is not on promotion than its considered as 0, and w500-1000gm mean is 0.011 and its standard deviation is 0.106 if the w500-1000gm is on promotion than we consider it as 1 and if the w500-1000gm is not on promotion than we consider it 0 and here the value is less than 1 so it is considered as 0.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Bonus	0.015	0.122	0	1
Surf Excel	0.012	0.110	0	1
Lipton	0.005	0.069	0	1
Deer Tea	0.012	0.110	0	1
Dalda Oil	0.015	0.122	0	1
Sunsilk	0.015	0.122	0	1
Store 1	0.038	0.191	0	1
Store 2	0.020	0.139	0	1
Store 3	0.020	0.129	0	1
Promotion	0.037	0.183	0	1
Weight 0 to500gm	0.063	0.243	0	1
Weight 500 to1000gm	0.011	0.106	0	1

Table 3: ANOVA Results for Brochure Advertising on Sales

Source	SS	DF	MS	F – Test	Significance
Model	22297	9	247741962	123.86	0.0000
Residual	20721	1036	2000116.76		
Total	43019	1045	4116553.71		

4.2. Revenues of different products relative to other products on store 3

All promotional products were considered to measure the relationship between the brochure advertising and revenue. The coefficient values of deer tea (2987.161), Surf Excel (721.595) and Lipton (3084.018) show the positive relationship with the sales. The coefficient value of Bonus (-670.0087) and Dalda oil (-377.9167) shows the negative relationship with sales. The p-value of all the independent variable is less than 1, shows all are significant,

Table 4: Results of the estimated model

Revenue	Coef.	T	p> t
Bonus	0.06700	4.09	0.000
Surf excel	0.07215	4.41	0.000
Lipton	0.30840	7.35	0.000
Deer tea	0.2987	6.70	0.000
Dalda oil	0.0377	2.31	0.021
Store 1	0.03943	3.66	0.000
Store 2	0.00402	0.28	0.776
Promotion	0.05590	3.35	0.001
Weight 500 to 1000gm	0.09280	2.02	0.000
_cons	0.0661	3.17	0.000

The coefficient value shows that Bonus 0.06700 is positive and generates more revenue relative to other products and significant at 1%. The coefficient value shows that surf excel 0.07215 is positive and significant at the 1% level of significance and generates more revenue relative to other products. The coefficient value shows that lipton 0.30840 is positive and significant at the 1% level of significance and generates more revenue relative to other products. The coefficient value shows that surf excel 0.2987 is positive and significant at the 1% level of significance and generates more revenue relative to other products. The coefficient value shows that Dalda oil 0.0377 is negative and generates less revenue relative to other products. The coefficient value also shows that the store 1 0.03943 is positive and generates more revenue relative to store 3. The coefficient value also shows that the store 2 0.00402 is positive and generates more revenue relative to store 3. The coefficient value shows that the promotion 0.05590 is positive and generates more revenue. The coefficient value shows that w500-1000gm 0.092800 is positive and generates more revenue relative to w0-500gm. This shows that the overall results are significant. Powel et al., (2010) explains about price promotions, on average, in supermarkets; price promotions were associated with 10.2% lower prices. The observed patterns of price promotions warrant more attention in public health food environment research and intervention. Estimated the coefficient majority of the products are the statistically significant, because the p value is less than 0.10. Researcher calculates the prices of each product which are the most estimated function are coefficients and prices.

Store is selling the detergent brand like surf excel relative to other products. It has a significant effect on the sales because the P value is less than 0.10. The quality of this product is not very much high that customer will pay the price so, that the customers are more concerning to pay less prices for this product. Therefore, Product name also plays an important role if the product does not have a high name and well-known value in the market that's why customer also feels hesitation to buy this product because of low price instead will encourage to pay less known brand name so that the brand name also effects on the sales of the promotional products that customer will pay easily. This result also gets support from other study (Roxburgh et al., 2015).

Store is selling the tea brand like lipton relative to other products. It has a significant effect on the sales because the P value is less than 0.10. The quality of this product is high and the customer will pay the price just for its quality. And if the products like that are on promotion than the attraction of customer towards these products. And these types of products always generate more revenue relative to other products.

Store is selling the oil brand like dalda oil relative to other products. It has a significant effect on the sales because the P value is less than 0.10. The quality of this product is high and the customer will pay the price just for its quality. And

if the products like that are on promotion than the attraction of customer towards these products. And these types of products always generate more revenue relative to other products.

5. Discussion

This theory derived by the way of to take a look at, there may be a fine relationship between the promotion through brochure advertising and sales the effects show this theory is general. The general results display that the promotion through brochure advertising has great impact at the sales which justifies the research. So, it may be concluded that the promotion through brochure advertising has a significant effect on retail sales.

Brochure advertising is a crucial tool for promoting retail sales in Pakistan, as consumers desire promotions on various products. This study aims to understand the impact of promotional discounts on store performance, the importance of non-traditional promotional factors, the role of display positioning, and the generalizability of the information.

The study uses advanced level models to evaluate the impact of promotional discounts on the performance of the promoted manufacturers. It also examines the role of non-traditional promotional factors, such as turnover, constant and variable prices, and alternate offers for various items. The study also examines the mediating position of displays and other unique advertising sports in the current market.

The study also examines the long-term effect of promotional discounts in different contexts, such as electronics, office components, and clothing. It also examines the impact of price advertising approaches, particularly reductions in advertising incidence, and the percentage of advertising in every category.

Market research and other research should be updated to promote brochure advertising in areas where traditional promotional strategies are lacking. This includes examining the segments of the market that are appealing and continuously seeking ways to attract more customers. A longitudinal study of households shopping for categories and types on deal, simple on merchandising, or both can provide valuable insights into the impact of different advertising strategies on sales.

6. Conclusion

This study aims to identify factors relating to brochure advertising in retail stores in Pakistan and its effect on sales. Data was collected from multiple retail stores and analyzed using the STATA data analysis software. The results showed that brochure advertising significantly impacts retail sales, as consumers are more interested in promotions on daily routine products. The research concluded that brochure advertising supports retail sales and increases consumer interest in promotions. The secondary method was used to collect secondary data from multiple retail stores in Punjab, Pakistan. The findings revealed that retail stores are constantly implementing powerful marketing packages for their products and services, resulting in strong advertising and marketing positions that encourage repeat purchases. The independent variable, promotion through brochure advertising, created a 52% variation in the dependent variable, sales, with a cost of 0.5127. The level of significance was 0.000, indicating a positive relationship between the two variables. The study concludes that revenues and promotions increase consumers, as they are an important part of the promotion process. Consumer reliability is crucial for the effectiveness of promotions and strengthens the orientation value effects in promotional periods. To improve the effectiveness of price promotion, retailers should focus on consumers and increase product lines.

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